

Rethinking Animal Welfare in Tunisian Animal Husbandry Law in the Context of Environmental Rights

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Abstract:

The Tunisian Animal Husbandry Law, enacted in 2005, sets the legal framework for farm animals in Tunisia. In the context of environmental rights, this article critically analyzes the Tunisian animal husbandry law and compares it with animal protection laws in other countries. This paper argues that Tunisian law is inadequate in several areas and concludes that Tunisia needs to adopt a more comprehensive and humane approach to animal welfare. This can be achieved by reforming the Animal Husbandry Law to take into account the latest scientific knowledge about animal rights.

I. Introduction

In contemporary times, the connection between environmental rights and animal welfare has gained growing attention.² While ensuring basic needs are met and minimizing suffering are important aspects of traditional approaches to animal welfare,³ there is a growing movement that acknowledges the wider environmental impact of animal husbandry. There is growing awareness that animals are sentient beings that should be treated humanely.⁴ This has motivated several nations to review their legal frameworks pertaining to animal husbandry methods. This pattern is also evident in Tunisia, a nation from the Global South with a strong agricultural heritage.⁵

Tunisian animal protection legislation has slowly evolved in recent years. The main law governing farm animals in Tunisia is Law 2005-95 of 18 October 2005 on animal husbandry and animal products.⁶ The scope of the law includes imported animals, animal products and animal feed. By focusing on the organization of the animal husbandry sector, this law recognizes the importance of sustainable animal husbandry practices that contribute to environmental protection.

However, the law's focus on animal agriculture and product quality may not fully address the broader ethical concerns surrounding animal rights, particularly when considering related but distinct rights of nature. New environmental laws are shifting from recognising a human right to a clean, healthy and sustainable environment to, in some cases, awarding rights to nature

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² Baoming Li and others, 'Research Progress on Animal Environment and Welfare' (2023) 1 *Animal Research and One Health* 78.

³ See E Szűcs and others, 'Animal Welfare in Different Human Cultures, Traditions and Religious Faiths' (2012) 25 *Asian-Australasian Journal of Animal Sciences* 1499.

⁴ For a more comprehensive discussion, see Saskia Stucki, 'Towards a Theory of Legal Animal Rights: Simple and Fundamental Rights' (2020) 40 *Oxford Journal of Legal Studies* 533.

⁵ Mohamed Azaza And Lída Colominas Barberà, 'Romanization and Animal husbandry in Tunisia: demand for wool?', in L Gourichon, C Daujeard, and JP Brugal (eds), *Hommes et Caprinés: De la montagne à la steppe, de la chasse à l'élevage* (Éditions APDCA, Antibes 2019) 243-254.

⁶ Loi n 2005-95 relative à l'élevage et aux produits animaux. Journal officiel de la République tunisienne n 83, 18 octobre 2005, p 2688 2694. An unofficial English translation of this law is available at this link:

< <https://fas.usda.gov/data/tunisia-law-animal-husbandry-and-animal-products> > accessed 29 August 2024.

itself, recognizing the interconnectedness of nature and its rights to exist and thrive.⁷ Rights of nature could be regarded as encompassing animal rights, which have developed separately, due to key principles including the right to exist, the right to habitat, and the right to fulfil ecological functions without human disruption.⁸

This paper delves into the limitations of the purely welfare-based approach to animal protection used in the Tunisian law, acknowledging the impacts of this on environmental protection objectives.⁹ It seeks to address a gap in current research by evaluating the interaction of Law 2005-95 with rights of nature, given the absence of existing literature on Tunisian animal regulations. In order to do this, the first section looks at the relationships between specific environmental rights and animal rights in order to create a conceptual framework. The second section then provides a comprehensive overview of the Animal Husbandry Law in Tunisia. Building on this foundation, the third section explores how different jurisdictions handle housing regulations under animal welfare laws. The fourth and final section offers a fresh framework for reevaluating farm animal welfare in Tunisia, arguing for legal reform.

II. A Conceptual Framework for Environmental Rights and Animal Rights

In recent years, there has been a growing recognition of the ‘interconnectedness of all living things’, as environmental philosopher Arne Naess put it.¹⁰ The notion that nature and animals have intrinsic value independent of their usefulness to humans has gained traction. Regarding animal well-being, there has been focus on both animal welfare and animal rights.

Animal welfare refers to the state of an animal’s overall wellbeing and how it is impacted by the treatment it receives including care, husbandry, and handling. Animal welfare is measurable and can be deemed poor even if an animal is not experiencing acute suffering.¹¹ On the other hand, animal rights, as discussed by Varner, reflect animals’ basic moral standing and, consequently, morally right and wrong ways of treating them.¹² This view is further supported by Francione (amongst others), who argues that animals have rights and should not be treated solely as means to human ends.¹³

The relationship between environmental rights and animal rights is complex and multifaceted. Garner and Wilson both highlight the interconnectedness of these rights, with Wilson emphasizing the need for an integrational approach.¹⁴ However, Faria argues that animal ethics and environmental ethics are incompatible, citing differences in moral considerability and normative implications.¹⁵ Stilt suggests that developments in environmental

⁷ Susana Borràs, ‘New Transitions from Human Rights to the Environment to the Rights of Nature’ (2016) 5 *Transnational Environmental Law* 113.

⁸ Hershel Raff and others, ‘Effect of Animal Facility Construction on Basal Hypothalamic-Pituitary-Adrenal and Renin-Aldosterone Activity in the Rat’ (2011) 152 *Endocrinology* 1218.

⁹ In this paper, we use ‘animal protection’ as a broad term encompassing both welfare-based approaches that minimize suffering and rights-based approaches that acknowledge inherent animal worth.

¹⁰ Arne Naess, ‘The Shallow and the Deep, Long-range Ecology Movement. A Summary’ (1973) 16 *Inquiry* 95-100.

¹¹ Syed Fazal ur Rahim, ‘Animal Rights and Welfare in Islam’ (2018) 3 *International International Journal of Avian & Wildlife Biology*.

¹² Gary E Varner, ‘The Prospects for Consensus and Convergence in the Animal Rights Debate’ (1994) 24 *The Hastings Center Report* 24.

¹³ See Gary Lawrence Francione, *Animals as Persons* (Columbia University Press 2008).

¹⁴ Robert Garner, ‘Environmental Politics, Animal Rights and Ecological Justice’ in Helen Kopnina and Eleanor Shoreman-Ouimet (eds), *Sustainability: Key Issues* (Routledge 2015).

¹⁵ Catia Faria and Eze Paez, ‘It’s Splitsville: Why Animal Ethics and Environmental Ethics Are Incompatible’ (2019) 63 *American Behavioral Scientist* 1047.

rights, such as the rights of nature, can provide valuable insights for the protection of animal rights.¹⁶ These perspectives collectively underscore the need for a nuanced understanding of the relationship between environmental and animal rights.

Animal rights theories can be linked to arguments for environmental protection. If animals have rights and interests of their own, then their habitats and environment must also be preserved in order to respect those rights. As Regan argues, animals are ‘subjects-of-a-life’ that can experience the world in their own right; they are not just objects for human use. The interests of animals and the environment cannot be separated.¹⁷

A key debate at the intersection of environmentalism and animal rights is the impact of industrial meat production on climate change and environmental sustainability. Modern industrial animal agriculture contributes significantly to climate change. The Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) estimated in 2023 that livestock production accounts for 11.1% of global greenhouse gas emissions.¹⁸ The vast majority of farmed animals are raised in confined, concentrated animal feeding operations (CAFOs) that generate air and water pollution. They also require massive amounts of crops, land, and water. By some estimates, growing feed crops for livestock consumes 56% of the water used in agriculture.¹⁹ The environmental impacts of industrial animal agriculture have led some to argue for a shift to plant-based diets and more sustainable agricultural practices.²⁰

These modern debates demonstrate the complex relationship between environmental protection and animal welfare. While the wellbeing of animals and the environment are deeply intertwined, policies and social changes aimed at benefiting one do not always align with the interests of the other. Additional research is needed to better understand how to balance these potentially competing goals and develop solutions that satisfy both environmental and animal rights concerns. Studies could also further explore the impacts of transitioning to more sustainable agricultural practices on both the environment and animals.

III. An Overview of the 2005 Tunisian Law on Farm Animals

The primary legislation pertaining to animal welfare in Tunisia is Law 2005-95 on Animal Husbandry and Animal Products, which is the only such law.²¹ The Law comprises 55 articles that are categorized into 7 titles. Article 2 defines animal husbandry as ‘the raising of walking animals for economic, cultural, sporting, or social purposes’. The term ‘herd’ refers to all types

¹⁶ Kristen Stilt, ‘Rights of Nature, Rights of Animals’ (2020) 134(5) *Harvard Law Review Forum* 276 <<https://harvardlawreview.org/forum/vol-134/rights-of-nature-rights-of-animals/>> accessed 29 August 2024.

¹⁷ Donald Scherer, ‘The Case for Animal Rights By Tom Regan. (Berkeley and Los Angeles: University of California Press, 1983. Xvii + 425 Pp. Notes and Index. \$24.95)’ (1985) 9 *Environmental Review* 77.

¹⁸ ‘Pathways towards lower emissions: A global assessment of the greenhouse gas emissions and mitigation options from livestock agrifood systems’ (FAO 2023) <<https://doi.org/10.4060/cc9029en>> accessed 29 August 2024.

¹⁹ Jens Heinke and others, ‘Water Use in Global Livestock Production—Opportunities and Constraints for Increasing Water Productivity’ (2020) 56 *Water Resources Research* <<https://doi.org/10.1029/2019wr026995>> accessed 29 August 2024.

²⁰ Mesfin M Mekonnen and Arjen Y Hoekstra, ‘A Global Assessment of the Water Footprint of Farm Animal Products’ (2012) 15 *Ecosystems* 401.

²¹ A close examination of Tunisia's animal protection laws and policy documents revealed critical gaps in environmental protection. The Tunisian Veterinary Police Law (1996) focuses narrowly on disease control and neglects measures to reduce pollution in industrial livestock farms. Similarly, the Tunisian Livestock Health Code (1975) and the Tunisian Poultry Health Code (2001) aim to ensure basic housing conditions for animals, but do not mandate sustainable waste management practices or limit the use of chemicals known to harm ecosystems.

of domestic or tamed walking animals of the same species that are typically raised in Tunisia, with a focus on bovine, ovine, caprine, camelids, equine, poultry, and small animals. This law focuses primarily on the regulation of animal husbandry and the production of animal products, and contains provisions on genetic improvement of the herd, slaughter of animals, transportation of meat, and protection of animal health.

On the other hand, unlike internationally recognized standards set by organizations like the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), of which Tunisia is a member, there are very few specific provisions pertaining to animal health and welfare. Provisions for the protection of animals from unnecessary suffering or cruelty are not included in the law, nor does it specifically address the welfare of animals in husbandry, transportation, or slaughter. Particularly in light of international standards, the lack of specific provisions pertaining to animal welfare raises questions about the sufficiency of legal protection for animals in Tunisia.²²

In addition, provisions guaranteeing animals' access to food and water as well as their protection from physical and mental suffering are not included in the law. The lack of such clauses in Tunisian animal husbandry law leaves animals vulnerable, exposing them to abuse and neglect. In fact the only substantive area addressed by this legislation is housing conditions. The consideration of housing conditions encompasses both its nature and condition. Examples of housing-related concerns include the allocation of living space, the choice to keep animals indoors or outdoors, the control of temperature and ventilation, and the building techniques and materials employed. In this regard, Article 22 states that:

Animal husbandry buildings and their equipment must be designed and equipped to ensure the welfare, cleanliness, and ease of movement of the animals.

The requirements for the structures and machinery mentioned in the first paragraph of this article are outlined in a book of specifications that the minister in charge of agriculture has authorized.

At a first glance, this Article has the potential to contribute to fostering an atmosphere that supports animal welfare. It acknowledges the importance of providing animals with suitable living conditions by establishing standards for animal buildings and equipment. In particular, the design and equipment of animal husbandry buildings are discussed in this Article, with a focus on the need to maintain animal welfare, hygiene, and mobility. A Book of Specifications authorized by the minister in charge of agriculture is to be followed when establishing the standards for these structures and machinery.²³

This Book of Specifications includes general technical conditions applicable to all animal husbandry and special technical conditions for particular species of animal. According to the general conditions, these habitats:

- Should be hygienic (Article 5);
- Should be fenced in a way that prevents strangers and other animals from entering, while taking into account the wind direction (Article 6);
- Should contain a basin for sterilizing shoes at the entrance (Article 7);

²² See World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH), 'Terrestrial Animal Health Code' (2021) <<https://www.oie.int/en/what-we-do/standards/codes-and-manuals/terrestrial-code-online-access/>> accessed 29 August 2024.

²³ Order of the Minister of Agriculture and Hydraulic Resources of October 21, 2006 approving the specifications setting the standards relating to livestock buildings and their equipment.

- Should have equipment that is not sharp (Article 8);
- Should be constructed with materials that are not harmful, easily cleanable, and sterilizable (Article 9).

The special conditions contain specific provisions applicable to bovine, ovine, caprine, camelid, equine, and poultry species. Animal welfare is not the primary focus of these conditions; rather, they aim to maximize productivity and safeguard public health, which is at risk due to factory farming methods.²⁴

While the general conditions outlined above include important provisions for animals' comfort, they remain incomplete. Firstly, the law sets a small fine for infractions. Because of this and the absence of a strong enforcement mechanism, these conditions are treated in practice as suggestions rather than imperatives. They provide farm animals with very little actual protection.²⁵ Secondly, these conditions are established by a ministerial order which holds less legal weight than a piece of legislation within the legal hierarchy. To have true legal force, they would need to be enshrined within legislation.

In order to guarantee that animal buildings and equipment comply with global best practices for animal welfare, the law may use some additional clarification on the standards underpinning them. This could include precise specifications for lighting, ventilation, space, and other elements that are important for the general welfare of animals in husbandry environments.²⁶

IV. A Global Perspective: International Best Practices in Animal Housing

As the scale and intensity of animal agriculture expands globally, farm animal welfare is an issue of increasing concern. These conditions have become a topic of increasing public interest and debate. Consumer attitudes are shifting in favor of alternative housing systems and higher welfare standards.²⁷ However, in the absence of comprehensive international regulations, legal frameworks from different regions can provide valuable insights into best practices for animal housing. By examining these best practices, Tunisia can identify areas where its own animal welfare legislation can be improved.

At the international level, the World Organisation for Animal Health's (WOAH) 'Five Freedoms' provide a fundamental framework for animal welfare, including freedom from hunger and thirst, freedom from discomfort, freedom from pain, injury, and disease, freedom to express natural behaviors, and freedom from fear and distress. While the WOAH Code mentions 'appropriate shelter' within this framework, it lacks specific housing standards.²⁸ However, there are further regulations of the European Union such as the Council Directive 98/58/EC of 20 July 1998 concerning the protection of animals kept for farming purposes. This

²⁴ In the same sense, see, Jonathan Anomaly, 'What's Wrong With Factory Farming?' (2014) 8 Public Health Ethics 246 <<http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/phe/phu001>> accessed 29 August 2024.

²⁵ According to Article 48 of the Law, any contravention of the provisions of Article 22 (paragraph 1) is punishable only by a fine of 100 to 500 dinars.

²⁶ For instance, the European Union's Welfare of Laying Hens Directive (2004/103/EC) sets specific requirements for minimum space allocation, nesting box design, and enrichment materials. This type of detailed approach could be a valuable model for this legislation.

²⁷ Jessica Aschemann-Witzel and others, 'Consumer-Related Food Waste: Causes and Potential for Action' (2015) 7 Sustainability 6457.

²⁸ Ch 7.1.

directive refers to freedom of movement, safe buildings and accommodation, proper air circulation, dust levels, temperature, and relative humidity and lighting.²⁹

National laws provide more detailed guidance on animal housing compared to these international and regional instruments, recognizing that different species have varying needs. For instance, the Swedish Animal Welfare Act (1988:534) serves as a strong example of how basic welfare principles can be translated into legal provisions. It contains several relevant provisions:

1. Livestock buildings and other holding rooms for animals shall be sufficiently spacious to allow all the animals to lie down at the same time and to move freely.
2. The premises shall be designed in such a way as to allow the animals to behave naturally.³⁰

According to this Act: ‘The fittings and other equipment shall not prevent the animals from behaving naturally, unnecessarily limit their freedom of movement or otherwise cause them inconvenience’.³¹

Similarly, the Austrian Animal Welfare Act 2004 focuses on safety by mandating that building materials and construction techniques pose no harm to animals. It declares:

1. Materials used for the construction and accommodation installations with which the animals may come into contact, and in particular for the construction of pens and equipment, must not be dangerous for the animals and be cleaned properly.
2. Accommodation and installations for tethering or caging animals shall be built and maintained in a way that there are no sharp edges or protrusions likely to cause injury to the animals.³²

Legislation goes beyond basic shelter to encompass climate control. In order to maintain fresh air and comfortable temperatures, buildings that house confined animals must have sufficient ventilation. Additional elements that contribute to animal welfare include proper lighting, noise reduction, flooring, and bedding.³³ The Austrian Act, for example, mandates that ‘[A person] who keeps any animals shall ensure that ... the climate, in particular light and temperature ... corresponds to their physiological and ethological needs’.³⁴ Similarly, the Taiwan Animal Protection Law Promulgated on 4 November 1998 requires keepers to ‘pay attention to the safe living environment, shelter, ventilation, lighting, temperature, cleaning and other appropriate care to prevent the animal from unnecessary harassment, mistreatment or hurt’.³⁵

Accommodating species-specific needs are crucial for safeguarding animal welfare. Recognizing this, the Austrian Act emphasizes that: ‘No animal shall be kept unless it can reasonably be expected, on the basis of its genotype or phenotype that it can be kept according

²⁹ See the EU version of this legislation on EUR-Lex at <<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/1998/58/2019-12-14>> accessed 29 August 2024

³⁰ s 1(b).

³¹ s 3.

³² ss 18(1)–(2).

³³ See Crista L Coppola, R Mark Enns and Temple Grandin, ‘Noise in the Animal Shelter Environment: Building Design and the Effects of Daily Noise Exposure’ (2006) 9 *Journal of Applied Animal Welfare Science* 1 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/s15327604jaws0901_1> accessed 29 August 2024.

³⁴ s 13(2).

³⁵ art 5.

to the state of the art of scientific knowledge without detrimental effect on its well-being'.³⁶ Similarly, the German Animal Protection Act (TierSchG) of 31 January 2008 states that 'any person keeping, caring for or required to care for an animal must provide the animal with food, care, and housing appropriate to its species, its requirements and behavior'.³⁷

Legislation pertaining to animal welfare often expressly allows for species-specific needs to be accommodated or directly addresses these needs because housing issues vary depending on the species. While not specifically addressing housing, the WOA Code does include summaries of species-specific issues in several of its chapters on animal welfare, which can inform the creation of particular recommendations.³⁸

V. Enhancing Animal Welfare in Tunisia: Recommendations for Legal Reform

Farm animal welfare is a multifaceted issue encompassing not just physical health and nutrition but also species-specific behavioral needs and the ability to live free from distress.³⁹ While focusing on welfare is crucial, achieving justice for animals might require a broader approach that acknowledges animals' inherent rights. This could help address the underlying injustices in the animal agriculture, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical industries.⁴⁰ Additionally, a more holistic approach is needed to fully capture the social and environmental entanglements of these industries.⁴¹

By addressing issues related to animal husbandry and protecting animal health, Law 2005-95 demonstrates a focus on animal welfare. However, concerns remain about how well this law safeguards environmental rights that, as introduced above, could be interpreted as including protection of animal welfare or animal rights as an essential element of safeguarding healthy ecosystems. Notably, the law lacks specific provisions on environmental rights or animal rights of any kind. This raises questions about the law's ability to comprehensively address the moral treatment of animals beyond safeguarding certain components of animal welfare.

The analysis conducted in this article indicates that, within the broader context of environmental rights, there is room for additional legislative measures that specifically address the welfare of animals. By establishing a conceptual framework that recognizes the interdependence of environmental rights and animal rights, this opinion piece was able to assess the present condition of animal welfare provisions in Tunisian legislation and, on that basis, can suggest reform. As an example of what could be done, offering protection to endangered species would not only safeguard biodiversity but would also ensure the well-being of those animals within their natural habitats. Or, regulations on factory farming practices to reduce pollution and waste could also improve animal welfare by minimizing stress and improving living conditions.

Taking an interconnected approach to environmental and animal rights may have substantial legal and policy ramifications. Recognizing the intrinsic value of animals and their role within ecosystems strengthens the connection between animal rights and human rights, particularly the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment. This holistic approach

³⁶ s 13 (1).

³⁷ s 2(1).

³⁸ Ch 7.3.12.

³⁹ Michael D Breed, *Conceptual Breakthroughs in Ethology and Animal Behavior* (Elsevier 2017) ch 29.

⁴⁰ J Baird Callicott, 'The Case for Animal Rights' (1985) 7 *Environmental Ethics* 365.

⁴¹ Brian Favre, 'Is There a Need for a New, an Ecological, Understanding of Legal Animal Rights?' (2020) 11 *Journal of Human Rights and the Environment* 297.

can strengthen the connection between efforts to alleviate animal suffering and ensure environmental protection and conservation efforts.⁴² Extending the reach and interpretation of specific environmental rights to encompass animal interests could better achieve justice for those who need it (i.e., animals experiencing suffering). It can also pose a challenge to the conventional anthropocentric understanding of rights by resulting in the recognition of rights of nonhuman animals and the environment.⁴³ In the context of Tunisia's 2005 Law on Animal Husbandry and Animal Products, a broader interpretation of environmental rights could inform legal frameworks that prioritize not just environmental sustainability but also the well-being of animals within those systems. This could lead to stricter regulations on factory farming practices that contribute to environmental degradation and animal suffering. Additionally, this could develop a governance approach that reflects the interrelationships within the natural world and humanity's proper place within it.⁴⁴ As this analysis of the Tunisian law has revealed, the limitations on animal welfare considerations highlight the need for a more holistic approach that recognizes the interconnectedness of environmental and animal well-being.

VI. Conclusion

In conclusion, while Law 2005-95 represents a first step towards regulating animal husbandry in Tunisia, a closer examination reveals significant shortcomings regarding animal welfare. The law lacks provisions on minimum space requirements, enrichment for farm animals, or prohibitions against practices like dehorning without anesthesia. These omissions fall short of globally accepted norms as outlined by the WOA. Additionally, the law lacks clear enforcement mechanisms, raising concerns about its effectiveness in ensuring animal welfare. These gaps highlight the need for a more comprehensive legal framework that prioritizes animal welfare protection in Tunisia.

This law does not prioritise animal welfare to the degree international standards and best practices from other jurisdictions would support. Noting also its narrow scope, there are concerns regarding how well the law protects the welfare and rights of animals in Tunisia. This highlights the need for a more holistic approach to animal welfare legislation in Tunisia, one that recognizes the interconnectedness of animal rights and environmental rights. As discussed earlier, applying environmental rights in a way that encompasses animal interests can promote a more sustainable and just future. By incorporating principles like the right to a healthy ecosystem and acknowledging the intrinsic value of animal life, Tunisian law could be strengthened to ensure the well-being of animals and the environment for generations to come.

⁴² Amy P Wilson, '(Non) Human(imal) Rights: Dismantling the Separateness in Law and Policy' (2020) 3 Society Register 39.

⁴³ Thomas NE Gray and others, 'Holistic Management of Live Animals Confiscated from Illegal Wildlife Trade' (2017) 54 Journal of Applied Ecology 726.

⁴⁴ Jeff Sebo and others, 'Sustainable Development Matters for Animals Too: Governments Have a Responsibility to Recognize That' [2022] CABI One Health.